

PRODUCTION COST ASSESSMENT

**Mechanical Engineering Degree
Manufacturing Processes II**

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Preliminary note

These notes are intended to support the teaching of the Manufacturing Processes II course unit of the Mechanical Engineering Degree at Instituto Superior Técnico. The document introduces the main concepts related to evaluating production costs, with a focus on their practical application in engineering contexts.

Structured in a progressive and accessible way for students with introductory knowledge of accounting and management, the text addresses topics such as cost structure in industrial companies, cost allocation methods, cost-volume-profit analysis, and production decisions based on the costs relevant for this purpose. Several illustrative examples are also presented, including the calculation of the breakeven point, the evaluation of special orders, and cost estimates for machined components and injection molded components.

The objective is to provide a solid foundation for understanding and applying economic analysis techniques in the context of production engineering, encouraging the integration of technical and economic decisions from the early stages of a product's design.

1. Introduction

When designing a new product, we must consider both the technical aspects, which depend on the materials used and the technologies involved, as well as the economic aspects.

Products are designed to satisfy customer needs, but in a competitive market, costs and price are determining variables for their commercial success.

On the other hand, for innovative products with little competition, the retail price can be set based on costs, specifically production costs, thereby imposing a profit margin. Therefore, evaluating or estimating product costs is important even at the design stage.

However, product costs have several components, some of which can be easily measured and others which must be evaluated using allocation criteria.

Product costs depend on the production process and the technologies adopted, as well as on other company activities and the organization and structure of the company. On the other hand, product costs also depend on market conditions, not only on the prices of the goods and services that the company must purchase, but also on demand and, consequently, on the quantities produced and sold.

To assess the different components of the cost of a unit of a product, we generally have to use and understand the accounting information produced by companies. However, this information assumes different characteristics depending on the type of user it is intended for, essentially distinguishing between two types of users: external users and internal users.

1.1 Accounting information for external users

Accounting information designed for external users is referred to as general, financial, or external, and its purpose is to provide a reliable representation of the company's financial situation and business progress.

This information is presented according to a predefined plan that is typically based on accounting standards established by international organizations, such as the [International Accounting Standards Board](#) (IASB), which the European Union adopts.

In Portugal, since 2005, companies listed on the stock exchange have followed the International Accounting Standards Board standards; however, most companies also use the "[Sistema de Normalização Contabilística](#)" (SNC), which is based on the international standards.

1.2 Accounting information for internal users

Accounting information for internal users is referred to as analytical or internal and is intended to provide detailed information relevant to those responsible for management, addressing their decision-making needs.

This information includes available accounting data and relevant market prices for decision-making purposes. This information is used to determine product costs and to provide data for controlling routine operations, such as setting prices, conducting profitability analysis, and deciding which types of products to market.

2. Cost structures and fundamental concepts

As already mentioned, the components of the cost of a unit of product depend on the company's activities and its organizational structure. However, to evaluate these costs effectively, we must always consider the available information and, consequently, how accounting information is presented to external users.

We are interested in evaluating the costs that may be incurred for a unit of a product or the implementation of a project; therefore, it is convenient to clarify what is meant by 'costs'. In accounting and monetary terms, we define cost as the measure of resources sacrificed to achieve a specific objective.

Since costs depend on a company's activities, we will now consider examples of Commercial, Industrial, and Service companies.

2.1 Commercial company costs

A commercial company's function is to facilitate the purchase of goods produced by another company for end consumers. Its main activities are Buying, Maintaining, Selling, Managing, and Financing.

With the Buying activity, costs associated with purchasing products, customs, and other expenses arise.

To Maintain the purchased products, storage costs and amortization of buildings acquired, or rents, may be necessary.

Associated with the Selling activity are the costs of sales personnel and other material resources.

In the Managing activity, we consider the costs of all other activities for which it is necessary to allocate people and other material resources.

With the Financing activity, the costs related to the remuneration of capital arise, for example, bank loans taken out by the company.

Considering all these costs, we can identify two groups of costs: Product Costs and Period Costs.

Product costs are those explicitly incurred to have the product available (they are related to its purchase).

Period costs are those that are generally incurred to enable the company to make sales (e.g., selling and administrative expenses).

In these companies, information on the costs and results of the company's activity in a given period (for example, a year) can be summarized in an Income Statement map, as shown below:

$$\begin{array}{r}
 \text{Sales} \\
 \text{(Cost of Goods Sold)} \\
 \hline
 \text{Gross Margin} \\
 \text{(Other Costs)} \\
 \hline
 \text{Net Profit Before Taxes}
 \end{array}$$

"Sales" represents the amount paid by customers for products sold by the company. The "Gross Margin" is obtained by subtracting the "Cost of Goods Sold" from "Sales".

Assuming that the company's activity is continuous but may vary from period to period, the quantity sold of a given product does not always coincide with the quantity purchased in the same period.

To address this situation, the "Cost of Goods Sold" can be assessed using the record of purchases made by the company in that period and by determining the variation in the value of products in stock:

$$\begin{array}{r}
 \text{Cost of Goods Sold} = \text{Purchases} \\
 \quad \quad \quad - \Delta \text{ Inventories}
 \end{array}$$

Next, by subtracting the value of "Other Costs" from the "Gross Margin", we obtain the "Net Income Before Taxes", which is an indicator of the company's performance during the analyzed period. "Other Costs" include the following components:

$$\begin{array}{r}
 \text{Other Costs} = \text{Amortizations} \\
 \quad \quad \quad + \text{Administrative and Sales Expenses}
 \end{array}$$

Amortizations represent the accounting value of the depreciation of the company's equipment and facilities during the period to which the data is reported.

Amortizations are not a cash flow (inflow or outflow of money), but they impact the amount subject to taxes (which is a cash outflow) and, therefore, the "Net Profit" that will be determined.

It is important to note that renting (equipment or buildings), even at the same amortization value that would be endured in the case of acquisition, does not have the same economic impact on the company. In the case of equipment amortization, for example, from an economic

perspective, it represents savings available to the company that will be used to replace the same equipment at the end of its useful life.

2.2 Costs of the Industrial Company

About the commercial company, the industrial company also includes the process of transforming raw materials into finished products.

However, manufactured products do not have a predetermined cost, unlike products that are bought for a fixed price and then sold with a profit margin. In this case, the costs of transforming them must be added to the purchase cost of the raw materials.

Therefore, to build the "Income Statement" for a given period of activity, we evaluate the "Cost of Goods Sold" as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cost of goods sold} &= \text{Cost of goods produced} \\ &\quad - \Delta \text{ Finished goods inventories} \end{aligned}$$

In turn, the "Cost of goods produced" can be assessed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cost of goods produced} &= \\ &= \text{Cost incorporated into manufacturing (Raw materials,} \\ &\quad \text{Labor and General production expenses (indirect))} \\ &\quad - \Delta \text{ Stocks of products in the process of being manufactured} \end{aligned}$$

Regarding raw materials, as they can be stored, the "Cost of raw materials used" during a given period of activity, for example, one year, can be evaluated as indicated below:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cost of raw materials used} &= \text{Purchases of raw materials} \\ &\quad - \Delta \text{ Inventories of raw materials} \end{aligned}$$

2.3 Costs of a Service Company

Service companies are similar to industrial companies as they involve both production activities, and administrative, commercial, and financial activities.

The difference is that a service is something intangible that is produced at the time it is sold. There are no raw materials, and therefore, most of the costs are period costs.

2.4 Cost Classification

To facilitate the processing of information related to costs, we can utilize several classification criteria depending on the study's objective or the report we intend to produce.

For example, when evaluating the costs of a unit of a product or a project, we can categorize the costs as either direct or indirect. In this case, we define direct costs as those costs that are unequivocally associated with the reference unit (i.e., the product, the project, or the production department). Indirect costs are costs

that are common to other reference units and must be allocated judiciously.

On the other hand, classifying costs as variable and fixed enables us to conduct several studies. For example, we can carry out a preliminary analysis of the economic feasibility of producing a particular product and establish the minimum sales level; we can also make decisions about the inclusion and exclusion of products in the production range; we can decide whether it is worth accepting a special order, among many other decisions.

In this case, we define fixed costs as costs that do not vary with the volume of activity. Variable costs are costs that vary in proportion to the volume of activity while remaining constant per unit of product. Of course, depending on the problem under analysis, we can refine this classification, defining, for example, semi-variable costs as those that can be broken down into a fixed and a variable part and semi-fixed costs as those that do not vary within a given interval but vary discontinuously between intervals. We can also use both classification criteria simultaneously. In this case, we can have the following combinations:

- a) Direct and variable costs: for example, raw materials, electricity (with a dedicated meter).
- b) Indirect and variable costs: maintenance and cleaning, electricity (with general meter).
- c) Direct and fixed costs: for example, amortization of dedicated equipment and technicians' salaries.
- d) Indirect and fixed costs: for example, rent of premises, administration salaries.

We can also identify unit costs and total costs. In this case, total costs refer to the costs associated with a batch of products, while unit costs pertain to the costs incurred per unit of product. Therefore, since total fixed costs are constant, the unit fixed cost varies with the volume of activity. On the other hand, the variable component of the unit cost is constant.

When we present unit costs, we also define the full cost as being the sum of direct costs and all indirect costs.

The full cost is significant in the development of new products. In this case, if the price is not defined, we can impose an expected profit margin and evaluate the sales price accordingly.

3. Cost centers

A cost center is an accounting unit for which cost data is collected and accumulated.

The division of the company into cost centers generally introduces greater rigor into the cost allocation process.

Cost centers do not necessarily have to correspond to departments; the process of classifying and accumulating costs can also be done by activity. The aim is to group costs into more homogeneous categories. To assign costs to products systematically, they can be grouped into three classes:

Direct and variable costs: These can generally be measured.

Direct and fixed costs: Their only difficulty is their dependence on the number of units produced in a given time interval.

Indirect costs: These are the main difficulty - they represent general costs that must be shared, first by the production centers and then by the products.

In this process, it is convenient to keep in mind that costs are either direct or indirect in relation to a specific reference unit.

3.1 Allocation of indirect costs

Once assessed, indirect costs for a given period must be allocated to products; to do so, they must first be distributed among the production centers (or activities). Then, taking into account the units processed in each center, they are allocated to the products.

The criteria for allocating indirect costs between production centers can be based on physical measures (e.g., square meters, cubic meters, machine hours, installed capacity) or accounting measures (e.g., fixed asset value, energy cost).

After being allocated to the production centers, indirect costs are allocated to products using criteria such as direct labor hours, machine hours, raw material costs, and total direct costs.

In the distribution of indirect costs between production centers, an additional complication may arise because non-production centers not only provide services to production centers, but they can also provide services to each other. In these situations, to assess the contribution of each service center to each production center, we can use, for example, one of the following methods (e.g. [2]):

Direct method: This method involves ignoring mutual services between service centers and dividing the costs of each one among the production centers in proportion to the services they provide to the latter. This is the simplest method, but it can lead to significant distortions if the mutual services are extensive.

Simultaneous method: This involves assigning a portion of the costs of each service center to the other service centers. In each service center, its direct costs are considered, as well as those attributed to it by others. This is the only correct method because it considers all interactions.

4. Cost-volume-profit relationships

Assuming that all costs related to the production and sale of a product have been assessed over a given period, we can determine the minimum quantity that needs to be sold for this activity to be profitable.

However, in the long term, for the company that produces this product to be economically viable, it is convenient for the production volume to deviate significantly from this minimum value, which is often referred to as the breakeven point.

To determine the breakeven point, we consider that the total costs of producing n units of the product can be classified into fixed costs (CF) and variable costs (CV). Also, considering the sales value (V), we obtain the pre-tax benefit (B) from the sale of n units:

$$B = V - CF - CV$$

The difference between the sales value (V) and the total variable cost (CV) is referred to as the total contribution margin (MC = V - CV). Thus, the previous relationship becomes:

$$B = MC - CF$$

Considering that the price of the product is p and that the unit variable costs are cv , the above relation can be written as follows:

$$B = n \times (p - cv) - CF$$

We can also define the unit contribution margin (mc) as the difference between the unit sales price and the unit variable cost: $mc = p - cv$.

Since the breakeven point corresponds to the volume of activity for which the company only covers its costs, i.e., has no profits or losses, we obtain the value of the breakeven quantity from the following expression:

$$B = 0 \rightarrow n_e = \frac{CF}{mc}$$

This result enables us to conclude that the total contribution margin (MC) corresponds to the volume of activity required to cover fixed costs. If it sells one more unit than the equilibrium quantity, it will have a benefit equal to mc . For each additional unit sold, the total benefit increases by mc .

This analysis is usually presented considering only one product. However, if the company simultaneously produces several products, it can also be performed by considering an average product, which can be defined based on the specifications of a sales composition.

5. Relevant costs for decision-making

Decisions related to production planning often involve selecting one alternative action from several possible options. In this case, the relevant costs for making a decision are estimates of future costs that we often make using accumulated data on the costs of previous production activities.

However, the fundamental issue is that when considering two or more decision alternatives and intending to choose one of them, we must identify which costs are common to all alternatives (unchanged costs) and which costs are unique to each alternative (differential costs).

Thus, to decide between the different alternatives that arise, it is necessary to calculate the difference between differential revenues and differential costs.

Differential analysis provides a relative ordering of the alternatives. In this way, we can find ourselves in situations where the best alternative is the one that causes the least damage.

The differential analysis also allows us to introduce the concept of the opportunity cost of an alternative, which represents the differential benefit that would be obtained in relation to the worst of the alternatives.

The process of evaluating the differential benefits of alternatives depends on the situation in which the company finds itself in terms of utilizing its production capacity.

To illustrate this dependence, we will consider two situations related to product decisions at low capacity and product decisions at high capacity. Product decisions are decisions in which the selling price is considered imposed.

5.1 Product Decisions at Low Capacity

A company is said to be operating at low capacity if it has available capacity that it is not using (i.e., excess capacity). In this case, the decisions we consider are related to the potential use of excess capacity.

For example, we can utilize excess production capacity to fulfill a special order for a specific product. To address this problem, we begin by noting that all additional costs associated with executing the special order are variable.

Therefore, the special order should be accepted if it provides a positive contribution margin and does not negatively influence the value of the selling price. In other words:

$$B = MC - CF$$

$$CF = Cte \Rightarrow \Delta B > 0 \Leftrightarrow \Delta MC > 0$$

We may also have to decide whether to add or remove a product.

Regarding the decision to remove a product, for example, with low capacity, it depends on the existence of direct fixed costs associated with the product and, therefore, on the estimated number of units that can be sold. The analysis of the differential benefit leads us to the following conclusions:

$$B > 0 \Rightarrow MC > CF$$

Therefore, we should continue to manufacture the product if its Contribution Margin exceeds the direct fixed costs of the product.

However, in the short term, since $MC > 0$, it will not be prudent to eliminate a product that may result in accounting losses (eliminating direct fixed costs may not be possible).

The decision to add a product is similar to the decision to eliminate one. However, there is the additional risk that the sales forecast will not be met.

5.2 Product decisions at high capacity

A company operating at high capacity corresponds to the full utilization of at least one of its resources or the allocation of its excess capacity to the production of other products.

Suppose a company has multiple resources, such as different workstations, and produces multiple products simultaneously. In that case, it is generally necessary to optimize the production level of each product to maximize the total benefit provided by the quantities produced of each product.

However, to illustrate the fundamental concepts involved in the decision-making process, we will first consider a scenario with only one product and one resource.

In this case, the decision to be made is about how to utilize the available production capacity most effectively. To do this, we evaluate the benefit of the units produced with the installed capacity as shown below:

$$B = n(pv - cv) - CF = \frac{mc}{t} HM - CF$$

In this expression, HM represents the production capacity (in machine hours, for example, 8 h/day), t is the production time of one unit

($t = HM/n$), and n represents the number of units produced per unit of capacity.

Therefore, assuming the same fixed costs for all decision alternatives, we should give priority to products whose contribution margin per unit of capacity (mc/t) is maximum.

6. Application examples

This section presents some illustrative examples of the concepts presented in the previous sections. Some of these examples are based on problems presented in references [1] and [2], which were adopted in the MBA that the author completed in 1994 at Universidade Católica Portuguesa in Lisbon.

6.1 Breakeven point for a new service

In product and service planning, the breakeven point assessment technique can be used to determine the volume at which total revenues or sales equal total costs. This technique allows several questions to be answered, including the following:

- Will the forecast sales volume be sufficient to generate a profit?
- Based on sales and price forecasts, what values of unit variable costs lead to positive profits?
- At what values of fixed costs is the profit positive?
- What is the influence of price on the breakeven volume?

To illustrate the application of this technique in the planning of new products or services, let us first consider the situation of a hospital unit that is considering introducing a new procedure to diagnose a health problem.

The fixed costs associated with this procedure are 100,000 Euros, and the variable costs are 100 Euros per patient.

If the service is provided at 200 Euros per patient, what will be the breakeven number of patients?

Solution:

To answer the question presented, we can use the breakeven analysis. We start by evaluating the contribution margin, simply subtracting the variable cost from the price of the service, as illustrated below:

$$mc = p - cv = 200 - 100 = 100 \text{ €/patient}$$

The breakeven quantity is obtained by dividing the total fixed costs by the contribution margin:

$$n_e = \frac{CF}{mc} = \frac{100\,000}{100} = 1000 \text{ patients}$$

To interpret this result, we can assume that the fixed costs correspond to the acquisition of new equipment, and that the variable costs correspond to consumables and the cost of the time dedicated to operating the equipment by a specialist.

Under these conditions, the equilibrium quantity represents only the cumulative number of patients that need to be treated so that the revenue generated by the new procedure exceeds its respective direct costs.

In this analysis, the time dimension, and therefore the duration of the equipment, was not taken into consideration.

On the other hand, if it is foreseeable that the hospital will have a demand for this type of treatment of more than 1000 patients per year, and if the useful life of the equipment is very high (e.g., 15 years), it is reasonable to assume that the introduction of the new procedure will be economically beneficial.

However, given the conditions of the statement, as we did not analyze the possibility of another procedure already being in operation for the same purpose or other investment alternatives, we cannot guarantee that investing in this new procedure is the best decision.

6.2 Breakeven point and sales targets

If, in a first approach, as in the previous example, the conclusions about the decision to be made are not obvious, or even if it is necessary to extract additional information to define, for example, sales targets, we can perform the breakeven point analysis for some time, considering only the costs of that period.

In this context, it is necessary to resort to the concept of amortization.

For example, suppose the dedicated equipment has an expected lifespan of 10 years, and we want to perform an annual analysis instead of considering the total cost of the equipment. In that case, we consider only 10% of its value. This corresponds to assuming that the equipment will depreciate and that after one year, its accounting value will be 90% of the initial value.

To illustrate the application of the breakeven point concept under these conditions, we consider the situation described below.

The sales price of the product is €60 per unit. The unit costs of the product, calculated based on a batch of 1500 units, are as follows:

Raw material	13
Direct labor	14
<u>Production overheads</u>	<u>12</u>
Production cost	39
Administrative costs	8
<u>Commissions</u>	<u>3</u>
Total cost (€/unit)	50

We consider that in this company, all production overheads are fixed, while labor is variable.

We intend to determine the product's contribution margin and the sales breakeven point.

Solution:

To evaluate the contribution margin and determine the breakeven point, we must first identify the variable costs and the fixed costs per unit. Variable costs are those that depend on the quantity produced, and, in this problem, they are "Raw Material", "Direct Labor", and "Sales Commissions":

$$cv = 13 + 14 + 3 = 30 \text{ €/un}$$

On the other hand, the unit fixed costs are "General production expenses" and "Administrative costs", totaling:

$$cf = 12 + 8 = 20 \text{ €/un}$$

Since the contribution margin is the difference between the selling price and the variable cost, we obtain:

$$mc = p - cv = 60 - 30 = 30 \text{ €/un}$$

To determine the breakeven point, let us assume that the batch of 1500 units corresponds to the estimated monthly production capacity. Under these conditions, we need to evaluate the total fixed costs for one month, and we proceed as shown below:

$$CF = 1500 \times cf = 1500 \times 20 = 30,000 \text{ €/m}$$

If the equilibrium quantity is n_e , from the condition $B = 0$, we obtain:

$$n_e = \frac{CF}{mc} = \frac{30\,000}{30} = 1000 \text{ un/m}$$

Therefore, for the company to make a profit from this activity, it must sell more than 1000 units of the product per month.

Based on the value of the equilibrium quantity, we can define the monthly sales target. However, to survive in the long term, the company must operate significantly away from the equilibrium point. Therefore, let's assume that we intend to sell 2000 units per month.

In this case, if the company sold 2000 units per month, the unit cost would be different from that shown in the previous table because the fixed costs would be divided among 2000 units instead of 1500. For example, the imputed "Production overheads" would be only €9 per unit, and the "Administrative costs" would be €6 per unit.

Therefore, the total effective unit cost would be €45 per unit, which is €5 lower per unit. The profit margin (MR) if sales were 1500 units/m would be:

$$MR = \frac{p-ct}{p} = \frac{60-50}{60} = 0.1667 = 16.67\%$$

However, if sales are 2000 units/m, we obtain a profit margin of 25%:

$$MR = \frac{p-ct}{p} = \frac{60-45}{60} = 0.25 = 25\%$$

6.3 Breakeven point with two products

The breakeven point analysis can also be applied when the company produces several products simultaneously. For these situations, we need the composition of sales, which is generally determined to optimize the total sales benefit.

To illustrate how to proceed in these cases, let us consider the example of a company that simultaneously manufactures two products, A and B, using only two machines, M1 and M2.

The problem data are as follows: to produce one unit of product A, machine M1 uses 16.2 minutes, and machine M2 uses 57.86 minutes. For product B, we require 32.4 minutes of M1 and 11.57 minutes of M2.

The machines are available 10080 minutes per month (8 hours per day and 21 working days per month), and the company's fixed costs are 4000 Euros per month.

The selling prices of the products are imposed by market conditions and are presented below, together with information on the variable costs and the optimal monthly production of each product:

	A	B
Selling price (p)	50.0 €	20.0 €
Unit variable costs (cv)	20.0 €	12.5 €
<u>Optimal composition of monthly sales¹</u>	<u>124 un</u>	<u>248 un</u>

¹ The optimal composition is obtained by solving a linear programming problem that maximizes the total contribution margin, respecting the available capacities of the machines.

Solution:

To assess the benefit generated by monthly sales, we can first assess the contribution margins of the products:

$$mc_A = p_A - cv_A = 50 - 20 = 30 \text{ €/un}$$

$$mc_B = p_B - cv_B = 20 - 12.5 = 7.5 \text{ €/un}$$

Next, we evaluate the total benefit:

$$\begin{aligned} B &= MC - CF = MC_A + MC_B - CF = mc_A \times n_A + mc_B \times n_B - CF \\ &= 124 \times 30 + 248 \times 7.5 - 4000 = 3720 + 1860 - 4000 = 1580 \text{ €/m} \end{aligned}$$

The occupancy rate of the machines can be assessed by dividing the time used to produce the products by the available time.

The time used by machine M1 to produce A and B can be assessed, as shown below, by calculating the time required to produce n_A units of A and n_B units of B in M1:

$$t_1 = t_{A1} \times n_A + t_{B1} \times n_B = 16.2 \times 124 + 32.4 \times 248 = 10044 \text{ min}$$

Since we have 10080 min available per month, the occupancy rate of M1 is 99.6%, or practically 100% (it is not 100% because the optimal solution was rounded to the nearest integer).

We can also show that machine M1 dedicates 20% of its time to product A and 80% to product B.

For machine M2, we also obtain an occupancy rate close to 100%, but in this case, 71.4% of the time is dedicated to product A and 28.6% to product B.

To determine the equilibrium quantity, we can write the expression for the total benefit as shown below:

$$B = n_T \times (mc_A \times \alpha_A + mc_B \times \alpha_B) - CF = n_T \times mc_T - CF$$

Being $\alpha_A = n_A / (n_A + n_B) = 124 / 372 = 1/3$ and $\alpha_B = 248 / 372 = 2/3$.

Under these conditions, we obtain $mc_T = 30 \times 1/3 + 7.5 \times 2/3 = 15 \text{ €/un}$.

Considering $B = 0$, we obtain:

$$n_{Te} = \frac{CF}{mc_T} = \frac{4000}{15} = 266.67 \text{ un}$$

Considering the proportions of sales of A and B, we obtain:

$$n_{Ae} = 266.67 \times 1/3 = 89 \text{ un}$$

$$n_{Be} = 266.67 \times 2/3 = 178 \text{ un}$$

Despite the simplicity of the calculations involved, this example allows us to draw some important conclusions, which we will discuss below.

In particular, we can see that if market conditions impose the price, then it is irrelevant how fixed costs are distributed between products A and B when deciding how to allocate machine time. The relevant variables for determining the optimal production plan are the contribution margins and the times required to produce a unit of each product.

When considering the simultaneous production of multiple products using the same resources, the optimal production quantity does not always favor the product with the highest unit contribution margin.

In this example, the product produced in the most significant quantity is B ($\alpha_B=2/3$), which has a much lower unit contribution margin ($mc_B=0.25mc_A$).

However, if we chose to produce only one of the products, we would obtain a different result. For example, if we chose to produce only B, we would exhaust the available time of machine M1, and we could produce a maximum of 311 units of B per month. This quantity would result in a total contribution margin (MC) of 2333.30 €/m, which would be insufficient to cover fixed costs. However, if we chose only to produce A, we would exhaust the available time of machine M2, and we could produce a maximum of 174 units of A. This quantity would provide an MC of 5226 €/m and, therefore, a total benefit of 1226 €/m. Therefore, if we had to choose only one of the products, we would favor product A over product B.

6.4 Unit transformation cost of a product

A company manufactures a single product in a two-stage production process in two different departments.

During the previous month, 1000 units were processed entirely in Department D1 and 1200 units in Department D2. The processing costs during this period are shown in the following table. The remaining costs, including management, communications, and others, are considered administrative and commercial expenses.

The monthly depreciation of the building is €2000 per month. The building has an area of 2500 m². Department D1 occupies 1000 m², and Department D2 occupies 1500 m².

We intend to evaluate the cost of processing a unit of the product.

Transformation costs (€/month)		
	Dep. 1	Dep. 2
Direct labor	1200.0	1500.0
Consumables and energy	300.0	150.0
Supervision	750.0	750.0
Equipment depreciation	1500.0	2250.0
	3750.0	4650.0

Solution:

The costs of processing products in each department are shown in the table above. We can see that one of the components of the cost is the depreciation of equipment, but the depreciation of the building is still missing.

Depreciation represents the consumption of the "Good" or "Asset" and has the effect of reducing taxes on profits.

Since we know the value of the building's depreciation, we can divide this value between the two departments using, for example, the relative value of the departments' areas as a criterion.

Since the relative values of the areas are 0.4 and 0.6, the €2000 depreciation of the building is divided into €800 for D1 and €1200 for D2.

If the building were rented, instead of depreciating the building, we would consider the rent that we would have to pay; however, the procedure for dividing the cost of the rent would remain the same.

However, in the case of rent, its value must be paid, whereas in the case of amortization, its value is only recorded; therefore, the long-term economic effect differs.

Based on the previous considerations, we obtain the total transformation costs as shown in the following table:

	Dep. 1	Dep. 2
Cost of transformation in departments (€)	3750.0	4650.0
Building depreciation (€)	<u>800.0</u>	<u>1200.0</u>
Total cost of transformation (€)	4550.0	5850.0
Processed units (un)	<u>1000</u>	<u>1200</u>
Unit cost of transformation (€/un)	4.550	4.875

Therefore, the cost of transforming a unit, after having passed through both departments, would be as follows:

$$cu = 4.550 + 4.875 = 9.425 \text{ €/un}$$

On the other hand, instead of using the relative value of the department areas to distribute the indirect costs of the building's depreciation, we could have used another criterion, such as the relative values of "Consumables and Energy". In this case, the

fraction of the building's depreciation attributed to D1 would be $\frac{2}{3}$ ($\frac{300}{450}$), and to D2 would be $\frac{1}{3}$. Therefore, D1 would be allocated €1333.32 and D2 €666.67. Under these conditions, the unit cost of transformation in the departments would be €5.083 and €4.431, and the total transformation cost would be 9.514 €/unit.

The values obtained using the two criteria are not significantly different. However, they illustrate that the unit cost of a product depends on several external factors, as well as the assumptions we must introduce for the distribution of indirect costs.

In this example, the total transformation cost depends on the indirect cost allocation criterion because it affects the division of costs between finished products and products in the manufacturing process.

6.5 Opportunity cost

To illustrate the concept of opportunity cost, consider the following example, which describes a situation where a company's raw material is suddenly devalued due to changes in market conditions.

The situation is as follows: the stocks of raw material X have become obsolete due to the emergence of a substitute product. Due to this change, the company must decide whether to sell raw material X as waste at the current market price of 2 €/kg (alternative A1) or to use it to manufacture a new product (alternative A2).

The new product can be sold for 20 €/unit, with each unit incorporating 1 kg of raw material X and requiring 10 €/unit of direct labor. Other production costs will not change due to the introduction of the new product.

The raw material initially cost 15 €/kg, the amount recorded in the company's accounts.

The company wants to identify the best decision.

Solution:

To identify the best decision, we must evaluate the benefits, in terms of revenue and costs, of each alternative.

Considering that alternative A1 is to sell raw material X, the unit benefit will be given by the difference between the market price at which the raw material can now be sold (p_m) and the acquisition price of the raw material (p_a):

$$B1 = V1 - C1 = p_m - p_a = 2 - 15 = -13 \text{ €/kg}$$

Alternative A2 involves using the obsolete raw material to produce the new product. In this case, the benefit per unit of raw material will be given by the difference between the sales value of the new product (p_2), per unit of raw material, and the costs per unit of raw material

required. Given that the additional costs of the new product are those of the raw material and direct labor, we obtain:

$$B2 = p2 - C2 = 20 - (15 + 10) = -5 \text{ €/kg}$$

Both alternatives yield negative benefits, but the second alternative is less detrimental than the first.

If we evaluate the difference between the two alternatives, we obtain:

$$B21 = B2 - B1 = -5 - (-13) = 8 \text{ €/kg}$$

In other words, B21 is the opportunity cost of alternative A2: it represents what we could lose by not choosing the best alternative.

However, the opportunity cost of alternative A2 can be assessed directly without the need to assess the benefit of the first alternative if, instead of the accounting value of the raw material, we use its market value, as shown below:

$$B2m = p2 - (pm + 10) = 20 - (2 + 10) = 8 \text{ €/kg}$$

In other words, the opportunity cost is the cost that we evaluate considering the market conditions at the time of decision-making and not the accounting values (which were recorded in the past).

The opportunity cost is a crucial concept in production management because it enables us to account for what can be lost by not adopting the best decision alternatives.

6.6 Evaluation of a Special Order

A company has excess production capacity and has recently received an order from a customer willing to purchase 100,000 units of product A for €10 per unit. The normal price of the product is 12 €/unit, and the available costs are as shown in the following table:

Raw material	4 €
Direct labor	2 €
<u>Overhead costs</u>	<u>5 €</u>
	11 €

Direct labor can be considered variable, as well as 10% of the overhead costs (i.e., general expenses).

The company concludes that it has the available capacity to fulfill the order but considers whether it is economically advantageous to accept the order.

Solution:

To answer the question posed, we must evaluate the differential costs of accepting or rejecting the order.

Based on the available information, we conclude that the differential costs are only those that change with the production volume; that is, they are the variable costs.

The variable costs are as follows:

Raw material	4.0 €
Direct labor	2.0 €
<u>Overhead costs</u>	<u>0.5 €</u>
	6.5 €

Therefore, the unit contribution margin for the special order has the following value:

$$mc = p - cv = 10 - 6.5 = 3.5 \text{ €/un}$$

Since the unit contribution margin is positive, the order should be accepted. For each unit sold, the company earns an additional profit of €3.50. For each additional unit sold, the accumulated profit increases by this amount.

The full cost (11 €/unit), which the company determined for normal production conditions, is higher than the price offered in the special order (10 €/unit), but it is irrelevant for making the decision.

6.7 Utilization of available capacity

A company has 100 machine hours to fill but can include products A, B, and C in its production range. However, demand for these products is limited to 70, 40, and 50 units, respectively.

The contribution margins and production time for one unit of each product are shown in the following table:

	A	B	C
mc (€/un)	10.0	13.5	8.0
t (h/un)	1.0	1.5	1.0

We want to know how to make the most of the 100 hours available.

Solution:

The production benefit of using the available 100 hours can be maximized using the following expression:

$$B = n(pv - cv) - CF = \frac{mc}{t} HM - CF$$

Where HM = 100 hours, and the fixed costs do not change whether or not we use the available hours. Therefore, the optimal distribution is obtained by first allocating the maximum production capacity to the products with the highest benefit per unit of time (mc/t).

The benefit per unit of time provided by each product, together with the demand (Q), are shown in the following table:

	A	B	C
mc/t (€/h)	10.0	9.0	8.0
Q (un)	70	40	50

This table shows that the product providing the highest profit per unit of time is A (10 €/h). Therefore, we begin by allocating the maximum amount of time to product A, ensuring it does not exceed the available capacity.

Since the demand for product A is 70 units, the hours required for this production are:

$$HM(A) = Q_A \times t_A = 70 \text{ h}$$

Therefore, we are left with $100 - 70 = 30$ hours to be filled.

Next, we consider the second product, which provides the highest benefit per unit of time, namely product B (9 €/h). However, in this case, we can no longer meet the total demand for B. Therefore, we will produce as many units of B as possible within the remaining 30 hours:

$$n_B = HM(B)/t_B = 30/1.5 = 20 \text{ un}$$

We would produce 70 units of A, 20 units of B, and no units of C. Under these conditions, the total contribution margin would be:

$$MC = MC_A + MC_B = 70 \times 10 + 20 \times 3.5 = 700 + 270 = 970 \text{ €}$$

6.8 Introduction of cost centers

A company has two sections, a mechanization section and an assembly section, which generally operate at full capacity. The accumulated labor time and accumulated cost data for these sections for the current year are as follows:

	Mecanização	Montagem	Total
Working hours (h)	5000	5000	10000
Labor cost (€)	75000	75000	150000
Cost of supervision (€)	10000	10000	20000
Equipment depreciation (€)	20000	6000	26000
Production overheads (€)	4000	4000	8000
Total (€)	109000	95000	204000

The company can consider each section as a cost center, or it can group them into a single cost center.

We intend to assess the impact of these alternatives on the costs of two recent orders using the following data: Order A utilized 120 hours of mechanization and 30 hours of assembly. At the same time, Order B employed 30 hours of mechanization and 120 hours of assembly.

Solution:

Let us consider only one cost center based on the data in the previous table. We estimate the unit cost of transformation per unit of time (ctu) by dividing the total accumulated cost by the number of working hours recorded, as shown below:

$$\text{ctu} = \frac{204\,000}{10\,000} = 20.4 \text{ €/h}$$

Therefore, since both order A and order B require a total of 150 labor hours for the transformation process, the total transformation cost (TC) is evaluated as shown below:

$$\text{TC(A)} = \text{TC(B)} = 20.4 \times 150 = 3060 \text{ €}$$

On the other hand, if we consider two cost centers, we estimate the unit cost of transformation per unit of time in each section by dividing the total accumulated cost of the section by the number of hours recorded in the section, as shown below:

$$\text{ctu(A)} = \frac{109\,000}{5\,000} = 21.8 \text{ €/h}$$

$$\text{ctu(B)} = \frac{95\,000}{5\,000} = 19.0 \text{ €/h}$$

Under these conditions, the processing costs for each order are assessed as shown below:

$$\text{TC(A)} = 21.8 \times 120 + 19.0 \times 30 = 3186 \text{ €}$$

$$\text{TC(B)} = 21.8 \times 30 + 19.0 \times 120 = 2984 \text{ €}$$

Since these values are more representative of the actual cost, we conclude that in the first alternative (with only one cost center), we would assign a lower cost to order A (3060 instead of 3186) and an exaggerated cost to order B (3060 instead of 2984).

If we assume that the sales price is proportional to the cost and that the same service can be provided by other companies, in the long run, we would attract many type A orders (because we would be charging a price lower than the market price) and few type B orders (because we would be charging a price higher than the market price), and this would contribute to a lower final profit than expected because the real profit margins would be lower than we would have anticipated.

6.9 Distribution of indirect costs

A company is composed of two production centers, A and B, and two service centers, P and Q. The costs, in a given time interval, of centers P and Q are 180,000 € and 90,000 €, respectively.

Center P dedicated 10% of its activity to providing services to Center A, 80% to Center B, and 10% to Center Q. Center Q dedicated 50% of its activity to Center A, 40% to Center B, and 10% to Center P.

We intend to evaluate the allocation of costs from service centers to production centers.

Solution:

Service center costs are indirect costs that must be transferred to production centers and then to products in order to be recovered through product sales.

Suppose the interactions between service centers P and Q are ignored. In that case, the distribution of indirect costs between centers A and B is made taking into account the proportion dedicated to centers A and B, as represented in the following table:

		P		Q	
A	1/9	20	5/9	50	70
B	8/9	160	4/9	40	200
		180		90	270

In the case of the costs of service center P, for example, since it dedicates 10% of its time to production center A and 80% to B, ignoring the interaction with service center Q, the part of the 180 k€ that is transferred to center A would be: $10/(10+80) \times 180 = 20$ k€.

In other words, production center A would absorb 70 k€, and production center B would receive the remaining 200 k€ of the total costs of service centers P and Q.

However, if the service centers did not help each other and had to resort to external services provided by self-help, their costs would be higher.

Therefore, a more accurate cost-sharing process involves determining the hypothetical costs of CPh and CQh that would have been incurred if the services received internally had been obtained from outside.

In this case, center P, for example, would have the costs that it paid externally, for 180 k€, but also the costs of the services that it received internally from center Q; that is, the hypothetical cost of center P would be:

$$C_{Ph} = 180 + 0.1 C_{Qh}$$

We can write a similar expression for the center Q, and we end up with a system of two equations, the solution to which is shown below:

$$\begin{cases} C_{Ph} = 180 + 0.1 C_{Qh} \\ C_{Qh} = 90 + 0.1 C_{Ph} \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} C_{Ph} = 190.9091 \\ C_{Qh} = 109.0909 \end{cases}$$

These are the indirect costs that are now distributed across all centers, taking into account the initial percentage allocation, as shown in the table below:

	P		Q		
A	0.1	19.09	0.5	54.55	73.64
B	0.8	152.73	0.4	43.64	196.36
P	-		0.1	10.91	270.00
Q	0.1	19.09	-		
		190.91		109.09	

As expected, the total transferred to production centers A and B is only the 270 k€ that was spent in centers P and Q.

Comparing this solution with the previous one, we conclude that in this case, production center A absorbs more costs, increasing from 70 k€ to 73.64 k€, while production center B receives only 196.36 k€ instead of 200 k€. This change in distribution can lead to differences in the unit price, as we saw in previous examples.

7. Production cost estimates

Estimating the cost of production is a key responsibility of engineers involved in designing components and new products. The ability to make these estimates develops with experience, aided by the project team and through interaction with product and service suppliers.

It is important to note that in the preliminary phase of development, it may not be easy to estimate all the components of the cost of a unit of the new product, but if it is possible to estimate the direct components, the remaining components can often be evaluated by comparing the relative values of the components of related products. Therefore, the analysis presented below is intended to contribute solely to the assessment of direct production costs.

In general, the unit production cost (C) of a component or product can be estimated using the following expression (e.g. [3]):

$$C = C_m + \frac{C_c}{n} + \frac{C_L}{\dot{n}}$$

Where:

C_m - represents the cost of the materials needed to manufacture the component (i.e., the balance of the value of the raw materials used);

C_c - is the cost of using the machines and tools involved in the process (i.e., energy, consumables, maintenance, and depreciation - or the equivalent economic rent) and also the cost of using the necessary facilities;

n - represents the number of components to be produced in the time interval T_n ;

C_L - is the cost of labor per unit of time;

\dot{n} - represents the number of components that will be produced per unit of time (i.e., $\dot{n} = n / T_n$).

To estimate production costs, very detailed information is required, as illustrated below by analyzing the cost estimates of two primary production processes: machining and injection molding.

7.1 Cost of machined components

Machined components are usually produced from a blank of raw material by removing portions of the material. Thus, machining costs depend mainly on the cost and initial shape of the raw material used, the amount and shape of the material that needs to be removed, and the accuracy with which it must be removed.

Based on these factors, seven control parameters that determine the cost of a machined component are identified in [3]. These factors and their influence are summarized below:

1. Type of material to be machined

The material used affects the cost in three ways: the cost of the raw material, the value of the scrap produced, and the ease with which the material can be machined.

2. Type of machines used

The type of machine used (e.g., lathe, horizontal milling machine, vertical milling machine) affects the cost of the component through the time the machine is used and the cost associated with the tools and accessories required.

3. Main dimensions of the component

The dimensions of the component determine the size of the machines of each type required to produce it. In general, the machines available have different operating costs, which depend on the initial cost of the machine and its age.

4. Number of surfaces machined

The number of surfaces that need to be machined directly influences the complexity of the component. The greater the complexity and the greater the percentage of material to be removed, the longer it will take to machine the part and the higher its production cost.

5. Number of components to be produced per batch

To produce a certain number of components on a machine, we must first configure it for the required operations. There is, therefore, a time dedicated to configuration (i.e., setup time) and a time dedicated to actual production. Thus, the average production time for each unit is evaluated, taking these two times into account. The relative value of setup time compared to production time can be high for low quantities produced and will be negligible for very high quantities produced.

6. Tolerances and surface finishes

The more stringent the tolerance and surface finish requirements, the more time and equipment required for production and the higher the cost of the components.

7. Labor cost per unit of time

If the machines used require an operator, the cost of the components will be higher the higher the labor cost.

Example 7.1

To illustrate the impact of the parameters that influence the cost of machined parts, we will consider a case study described in [3]. This problem was presented together with a mathematical model developed in Excel, which can be obtained by following the link below.

[14 * Machined part cost calculator](#)

The technical drawing of the part to be produced is shown in Figure 11.6, on page 324 of [3].

The main characteristics of this part, relevant to evaluating the production cost, are those presented in the data table of the model developed in Excel, which is shown in Figure 1 and described below.

As we can see, at the top, we need to define the Type of metal (Low-carbon steel), the Initial format of the raw material (Bar), the Main machining process (Lathe), the Surface finish (Intermediate), and the Dimensional tolerance (Fit).

Input			
What Metal?	Low Carbon Steel	What Raw Material Shape?	Bar
		What Primary Macining Process?	Lathe
		What finish?	Intermediate
		What tolerance?	Fit
length	4 in	Other machines	2
outside diameter	2.25 in	Parts per Batch	100
inside diameter	0 in	Hourly rate	35 \$
Volumetric Ratio (1-99)	32		
Number of Faces	7		
Number of diameters	3		

Figure 1 - Data table of the model for evaluating the production cost of a machined part²

Next, we have a box where we define the reference dimensions of the part (in inches): the length (4 in), the largest external diameter of the part (2.25 in), and a reference internal diameter (which does not exist in this part). Still, in the same box, we have the relative value between the final volume of the part and the initial volume of the block of raw material that gave rise to it (32%), the number of flat surfaces of the part (7), and the number of curved surfaces (3).

In the second box below, we define the number of other machines that will also be necessary to obtain the final product (2), the number of parts in the batch that we intend to produce (100), and the labor rate used (35 \$/h).

The simulation results are presented in both a graph and a table, which we reproduce in Figure 2.

² Reproduction of the data entry section of the main page of the file "14_Machining_cost.xls" downloaded from the link shown above.

Results	
Part Wt	1.440 lb
Material Cost/lb	0.330 \$
Material Cost/part	1.485 \$
Mach time/part	0.313 hr
Labor cost/part	10.947 \$
Total cost	12.431 \$

Figure 2 - Results table of the model for evaluating the production cost of a machined part

As we can see, first, we have information about the final weight of the part (1.440 lb) and the unit cost of the raw material. Below, we provide information about the average production time of a part, as well as details on two key cost components: the cost of raw materials and the cost of labor.

The cost component related to the use of machines and tools involved in the process was not considered, as it was assumed to be insignificant in this case.

To illustrate how the cost of a part varies with the batch size, we present the simulation results in the table below for batches of 100, 200, and 300 parts.

Table 1 - Production cost of a machined part according to batch size

Parts per Lot	100	200	300
Material Cost (\$/part)	1.485	1.485	1.485
Machine Time (h/part)	0.3128	0.2905	0.2831
Labor Cost (\$/part)	10.947	10.169	9.910
Total Cost (\$/part)	12.431	11.654	11.395

The simulation results, presented in Table 1, indicate that the cost decreases with increasing batch size because the time required to produce a unit decreases, resulting in a reduction in labor cost per piece. This happens because the relative value of the setup time decreases.

To better analyze the problem, we can determine the setup time used internally by the model, considering the following relationship:

$$T_n = T_{set} + T_{wp} \times n$$

Where T_{set} represents the setup time (i.e., the machine setup time), T_{wp} represents the time used per part (i.e., the actual machining time), and T_n is the total production time of n parts.

Using the simulation results for batches of 100 and 200 parts, presented in Table 1, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} 0.3128 \times 100 &= T_{set} + T_{wp} \times 100 \\ 0.2905 \times 200 &= T_{set} + T_{wp} \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

By solving the system of equations, we obtain:

$$T_{set} = 4.44167 \text{ h}$$

$$T_{wp} = 0.26834 \text{ h/un}$$

With this information, we can check the value of the average time required per unit (T_{mp}) for the batch of 300 units:

$$T_{mp} = T_{set}/n + T_{wp} = 4.44167/300 + 0.26834 = 0.28314 \text{ h/un}$$

It is, therefore, confirmed that the value of T_{mp} we obtained, with the calculated values of T_{wp} and T_{set} , coincides with the value presented in Table 1, which the model generated.

Although the production cost decreases with the batch size, this does not mean that it will always be advantageous for the company to produce a large number of parts per batch, as there may not be sufficient demand, and other important costs, such as storage costs, may also be incurred.

The production cost of the part depends on all the parameters that can be changed in the data table shown in Figure 1. In the following table, we compare the production cost for different surface finishes (considering a batch of 100 parts): Rough, Intermediate, and Fine.

Table 2 - Production cost of a machined part according to surface finish

<u>Finishing:</u>	<u>Rough</u>	<u>Intermediate</u>	<u>Fine</u>
Material cost (\$/part)	1.485	1.485	1.485
Machine time (h/part)	0.219	0.313	0.438
Labor cost (\$/part)	7.663	10.947	15.325
<u>Total cost (\$/part)</u>	<u>9.147</u>	<u>12.431</u>	<u>16.810</u>

The results presented in this table show that the average production time increases significantly with the increase in the finishing level. If we consider the results for other production batches, we can determine the setup times and the times used per part for the two new situations presented in the table.

In the case of rough finishing, we obtain $T_{set} = 3.109$ hours and $T_{wp} = 0.188$ hours per part, and for fine finishing, we obtain $T_{set} = 6.218$ hours and $T_{wp} = 0.376$ hours per part. Therefore, the desired finishing level affects both the setup time and the actual time spent on each part.

7.2 Cost of injection molded components

Plastic injection molding is a production method that allows for great flexibility in component shape but is only economically viable for high production volumes, typically exceeding 1 million units.

Generally, all factors that affect the cost of machined components also impact the cost of injection-molded components. However, in this case, we consider only one type of machine, the injection molding machine, and the issues related to the part's geometry are different.

In addition to the main dimensions of the component, it is important to know the wall thickness and the complexity of the component. These factors influence the size of the molding machine required, the time required for the components to cool sufficiently for extraction, the number of mold cavities (the number of components molded at one time), and the cost of the mold.

Example 7.2

To illustrate the impact of the parameters that influence the cost of parts produced by plastic injection molding, we will analyze a case study described in [3]. This problem was also presented together with a mathematical model developed in Excel, which can be obtained by following the link below.

[13 * Plastic part cost calculator](#)

The technical drawing of the part to be produced is shown in Figure 11.8, on page 326 of [3]. The characteristics of the part relevant for evaluating the production cost are those that appear in the data table of the model used, which we present in Figure 3 and describe below.

Shape of part Box	Part complexity Intermediate	What finish? Not critical
Units cm	What tolerance? Intermediate	What material? Polystyrene
Length	9.46	
Width	4.52	
Depth into mold	4.13	
Wall thickness	0.32	
Parts to be made	1000000	
Hourly rate	35	\$

Figure 3 - Data from the model for evaluating the production cost of a part using plastic injection molding³

³ Reproduction of the data entry section of the main page of the file "13_Plastic_Cost.xls" downloaded from the link shown above.

In this case, at the top, we begin by defining the shape of the part (Box) and the complexity (Intermediate), the tolerance (Intermediate), the finish (Non-critical), and the type of material (Polystyrene).

As shown in Figure 11.8 of [3], the relevant dimensions of the part are 9.46 cm and 4.52 cm in the mold plane and 4.13 cm in depth. The wall thickness of the part is 0.32 cm.

The labor cost is \$35 per hour.

In Table 3, we present the production cost of the component, considering three production volumes: 10,000, 100,000, and 1000,000 parts.

Table 3 – Production cost of a Polystyrene part according to batch size

Number of Parts	10,000	100,000	1000,000
Number of Cavities	1	1	3
Total mold most (\$)	37726	37726	93898
Cycle time her heat (s)	8.03	8.03	2.68
Labor cost per part (\$)	0.17	0.17	0.05
Mold cost per part (\$)	3.77	0.38	0.09
Material cost per part (\$)	0.08	0.08	0.08
Labor cost per part (\$)	0.17	0.17	0.05
Total cost per part (\$)	4.19	0.79	0.28

In this table, we can see that for low production volumes (10,000 units), the cost component due to the mold (Mold cost per part) is significantly higher than the others. For high production volumes, the different components are of the same order of magnitude.

The simulation results table also presents information on the cooling time required to extract the parts. The total production time of a part (T_{mp}) can be broken down into two parts: one for injection (T_{in}) and the other for cooling and extraction (T_{ex}).

The total production time of the batch of parts (T_n) can be evaluated by calculating the total labor costs required to produce all the parts and then dividing the result by the hourly labor cost. In this way, we obtain the results presented in the following table:

Table 4 – Production cost of 3 batches of Polystyrene parts and production and injection times

Number of Parts	10,000	100,000	1000,000
Total cost (\$)	41875	79216	278509
Mold cost (\$)	37726	37726	93894
Material cost (\$)	832	8321	83208
Labor cost (\$)	3317	33169	101406
T_n (h)	94.80	947.70	2897.30
T_{mp} (s/part)	34.12	34.12	10.43
T_{in} (s/part)	26.09	26.09	7.76

The two tables above illustrate that production costs are significantly influenced by the type of mold selected. Unfortunately, this is a parameter that we do not directly control in the spreadsheet. The model automatically adjusts the mold cost depending on the quantity to be produced. However, for high production volumes, the mold is significantly more expensive but can also produce multiple parts simultaneously. The injection and cooling times per part are also shorter, which helps reduce labor-related costs.

The tests conducted with variations in tolerance and finishing parameters did not yield significant changes. However, changing the material to Polypropylene resulted in some differences, which we show in the following tables.

Table 5 - Production cost of a Polypropylene part according to batch size

<u>Number of Parts</u>	<u>10,000</u>	<u>100,000</u>	<u>1000,000</u>
<u>Number of Cavities</u>	<u>1</u>	<u>1</u>	<u>3</u>
Total mold cost (\$)	37726	37726	100100
Cycle time per heat (s)	9.22	9.22	3.07
Labor cost per part (\$)	0.19	0.19	0.05
Mold cost per part (\$)	3.77	0.38	0.10
Material cost per part (\$)	0.08	0.08	0.08
<u>Labor cost per part (\$)</u>	<u>0.19</u>	<u>0.19</u>	<u>0.05</u>
Total cost per part (\$)	4.24	0.84	0.29

We can see that the cost of the material remains the same, but the components are now slightly more expensive. For smaller volumes, the mold cost remains the same; however, for larger volumes, this cost increases slightly. However, the time required for cooling increases, which will directly influence the labor cost.

In turn, the results in the following table, when compared with those in Table 4, confirm that the time required to produce a component increases and also confirm that both components of this time increase.

Table 6 - Production cost of 3 batches of Polypropylene parts and production and injection times

<u>Number of Parts</u>	<u>10,000</u>	<u>100,000</u>	<u>1000,000</u>
<u>Total cost (\$)</u>	<u>42370</u>	<u>84166</u>	<u>290463</u>
Mold cost (\$)	37726	37726	100100
Material cost (\$)	832	8321	83208
<u>Labor cost (\$)</u>	<u>3812</u>	<u>38119</u>	<u>107155</u>
Tn (h)	108.9	1089.1	3061.6
Tmp (s/part)	39.21	39.21	11.02
<u>Tin (s/part)</u>	<u>29.99</u>	<u>29.99</u>	<u>7.95</u>

8. References

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